

MEDICAL SCIENCES

SOME ASPECTS OF RADIATION PROTECTION IN NUCLEAR MEDICINE DEPARTMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Nuclear medicine is a medical specialty that uses radioactive substances or radiopharmaceuticals combined with imaging techniques to diagnose and treat various diseases or injuries. In diagnostic applications, nuclear imaging allows physicians to study bodily functions while they are taking place. In therapeutic applications, high radiation doses are used to destroy diseased tissues. The aim of this paper is to emphasize the very important aspects regarding the radiation protection that have to be considered and applied when it is designing a new nuclear medicine department and/or daily work in it. In our country today, several specialized units, known as nuclear medicine clinics, operate using radioactive isotopes and nuclear radiation either *in vivo* or *in vitro* for diagnostic and therapeutic purposes. The prospects for the use of nuclear methods in medicine are clear and optimistic for the future. Although some physicians practice nuclear medicine as a full specialty, others working in radiology, pathology, and internal medicine use aspects of nuclear medicine in their daily work. At its most basic level, nuclear imaging examines chemical reactions occurring within the human body. To produce an image, a radioactive substance is administered orally or by injection. During this work has to be specified minimum standards of safe design, responsibility of personnel in the department, how to achieve optimization of medical exposure and minimize the worker and public exposure, deal with radiation sources and waste management, how to prevent accident and deal with it if happened.

Keywords: Nuclear medicine, radiation protection, radiopharmaceuticals, radioactive source, waste management.

Introduction

In our country today, several specialized units, known as nuclear medicine clinics, operate using radioactive isotopes and nuclear radiation either *in vivo* or *in vitro* for diagnostic and therapeutic purposes. The prospects for the use of nuclear methods in medicine are clear and optimistic for the future. Although some physicians practice nuclear medicine as a full specialty, others working in radiology, pathology, and internal medicine use aspects of nuclear medicine in their daily work. At its most basic level, nuclear imaging examines chemical reactions occurring within the human body. To produce an image, a radioactive substance is administered orally or by injection.

Radiation Protection in Nuclear Medicine

Many structured guidelines or recommendations of various academic societies or international campaigns demonstrate important issues of radiation safety in nuclear medicine procedures. There are ongoing efforts to fulfil the basic principles of radiation protection in daily nuclear medicine practice (1).

The design of the Nuclear Medicine Facilities should take into consideration the type of work and the radionuclides and their activities intended to be used. The concept of categorization of hazard should be used to determine the special needs concerning ventilation, plumbing, materials used in walls, floors and work benches. The main objectives of adequate design of a nuclear medicine facility can be summarized in the following points: safety of sources, optimize exposure of staff, patients and public, prevent uncontrolled spread of contamination, maintain low background where most needed and fulfil requirements regarding pharmaceutical work. Building requirements include

floors (that should be covered with one sheet of a material with impervious, washable, chemical-resistant material, curved to the walls, all joints sealed, glued to the floor). Walls and ceiling (that should be finished in a smooth and washable surface with joints being sealed, wherever practicable and walls should be painted with washable, non-porous paint). Worktop surfaces (that must be finished in a smooth, washable and chemical-resistant surface with all joints sealed. Regarding ventilation (laboratories in which unsealed sources, especially radioactive aerosols or gases, may be produced or handled should have an appropriate ventilation system that includes a fume hood, laminar air flow cabinet or glove box. The ventilation system should be designed such that the laboratory is at negative pressure relative to surrounding areas. The airflow should be from areas of minimal likelihood of airborne contamination to areas where such contamination is likely. All air from the laboratory should be vented through a fume hood and must not be recirculated either directly, in combination with incoming fresh air in a mixing system, or indirectly, because of proximity of the exhaust to a fresh air intake.

The fume hood must be constructed of smooth, impervious, washable and chemical resistant material. The working surface should have a slightly raised lip to contain any spills and must be strong enough to bear the weight of any lead shielding that may be required.

Operational Areas and Safety

The area of imaging room shall depend on the size of gamma camera and other associated equipment and accessories that may present in the room however typically the room area should be about 25m. The imaging room shall be a separate room from the

dispensing laboratory and shall be well shielded from any radiation source other than the patient. The laboratory shall be of sufficient size to allow ease of use. Separate work surfaces shall be provided for handling radioactive materials and doing bookwork. The hot lab must be located away from public places, office areas and areas where security cannot be guaranteed. Direct access to the hot lab should only be available from another laboratory, laboratory corridor. Any work bench where radioactive materials that emit gamma or high energy beta radiation are handled shall be equipped with a shielded workstation. This should be provided with a screen of lead glass or lead Perspex for gamma radiation, or Perspex or other clear plastic for beta radiation. In most cases an overshoe barrier should be installed. The barrier may be the simple step over type (approx. 20cm in height) or be more substantial allowing persons a sitting area while they apply overshoes. They may also contain shoe and overshoe storage areas. An inpatient treated with more than 400MBq of I - 131 should be located in a single bedroom equipped with its own toilet and shower or bathroom (isolation rooms). The flooring should be smooth, continuous, and non-absorbent. The walls and furniture should be covered with a non-absorbent surface for ease of decontamination. The bed should be located as remotely as possible from other hospital beds in neighbouring rooms. Depending on the wall construction some extra shielding may be necessary.

Occupational and Medical Exposure

Areas in a nuclear medicine department should be clearly defined as part of the Radiation Protection Plan (RPP) and their classification should result from safety assessment. Two types of area may be defined controlled areas or supervised areas (Controlled area and Supervised area). When considering possible health effects to nuclear medicine patients or occupationally exposed personnel, it also is important to place the dose received in perspective by considering the radiation dose received by all of us from natural background sources (2). Individual dose monitoring shall be undertaken for workers who are normally exposed to radiation in controlled areas e.g., medical physicists, the RPO, technologist and nurses. Other users of radioisotope sources, such as clinical specialists, research staff and ancillary workers who frequently work in controlled areas, should also be individually monitored. Individual external doses shall be determined by using individual monitoring devices approved by the Regulatory Authority, thermoluminescent dosimeters, film badges or other devices. Periodic monitoring with a survey meter and contamination monitors or by wipe tests should be conducted for controlled and supervised areas, Laboratories and other areas in which work with unsealed sources is undertaken should be monitored, both for external radiation and for surface contamination, on a systematic basis. Contamination monitoring is required for all working surfaces, floor, protective and personal clothing, clothing and bedding of therapy patients and any items removed from controlled areas. To comply with radiation safety it is indispensable that licensees establish an internal mechanism to ensure that medical exposure be

prescribed by a medical practitioner, that the obligation for overall patient protection be assigned to a nuclear medicine specialist or equivalent, that medical and paramedical staff be available, that advice of qualified experts in nuclear medicine physics be available, and that only staff with the necessary training be in charge of exposure of patients for diagnosis and treatment.

Justification

Medical exposures should be justified by weighing the diagnostic or therapeutic benefits they produce against the radiation detriment they might cause, considering the benefits and risks of available alternative techniques that do not involve medical exposure, such as ultrasound or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). As children are at greater risk of incurring stochastic effects, pediatric examinations should require special consideration in the justification process. Thus, the benefit of some high dose examinations should be carefully weighed against the increased risk. The justification of examinations in pregnant women requires special consideration.

Optimization

For diagnostic procedures, the optimization process necessarily requires a balance between administered activity (and patient radiation dose) and image quality. The activity administered should be sufficient to produce good image quality.

For therapeutic procedures an effective system for identification of patients should be in place, procedures to find out, before administration of the radiopharmaceutical, whether patients are pregnant or breast feeding, verbal and written instructions to patients to minimize exposure to family members and the public, special attention to preventing spread of contamination due to patient vomit and excreta, observance of national regulations on release of patients after administration of therapeutic doses of radiopharmaceuticals.

Public Exposure

Public exposure is controlled, in large part, by always ensuring that radiation sources, (usage, transport, storage or disposal) are secure to prevent unauthorized access or use. Access by members of the public to areas in and near the nuclear medicine department should be considered when designing and shielding storage and use locations. This should include access by other members of the hospital staff, including housekeeping, maintenance, and medical staff who may have legitimate reasons to be in the department.

Radioactive sources and waste management

Source stores must provide protection against environmental conditions, be only for radioactive materials, provide sufficient shielding, be resistant to fire and be secure. The objective of source security is to always ensure continuity in the control and accountability of each source. The licensee shall establish security systems to prevent theft, loss, unauthorized use, or damage to sources, or entrance of unauthorized personnel to the controlled areas. The licensee shall maintain an inventory of sources received by the practice and develop procedures to always ensure the safe movement of radioactive sources within the institution from receipt to disposal. The use of unsealed sources in diagnosis and therapy will generate

radioactive waste of different kinds during preparation, patient examination and care. Radioactive waste needs to be safely managed because it is potentially hazardous to human health and the environment. Inadequate management after use or loss of radioactive material, especially sealed radiation sources, has resulted in radiation exposure of members of the public or extensive contamination of equipment, buildings or land. In some cases, uncontrolled radiation exposure has been lethal. Radioactive waste from nuclear medicine procedures can be dealt with either by simply storing the wastes safely till radioactive decay reduces the activity to a safe level or possibly by disposal of low-activity waste into the sewage system (3). The radioactive waste in hospitals comprises many different types of waste. It may be of high activity such as a technetium generator and sources used in radionuclide therapy, or low activity waste from biomedical procedures or research. It may be in solid, liquid or gaseous form. All these aspects must be accounted for in the planning of waste treatment in a hospital. The types of waste are solid waste that include cover papers, gloves, empty vials and syringes, radionuclide generators, items used by hospitalized patients after radionuclide therapy, sealed sources used for calibration of instruments. Another type of waste is liquid waste in forms of residues of radionuclides, patient excreta and liquid scintillation solutions. Gaseous waste in form of exhausted gas from patients in nuclear medicine is the last typology of waste we discuss in this article. The registrant and the licensee shall develop and implement a program for safe disposal of radioactive waste or return of sources when their use is discontinued, as required by the regulation of management of radioactive waste.

Waste collection and segregation and storage

In order to simplify the waste management the selection of unsealed sources in a certain application should consider: the half-life of the radionuclide, which should be as short as is consistent with the application, the type and energy of the radiation, the activity, which should be as low as is consistent with the application selection of materials that minimize the number of operations required to prepare them for the specific application. Containers to allow segregation of different types of radioactive waste should be available in areas where the waste is generated (mainly, the hot lab.). The containers must be suitable for that purpose (volume, shielding, leak proof, etc.). Each type of waste should be kept in separate containers properly labeled to supply information about the radionuclide, activity concentration etc. Flammable goods should be kept apart. A room for interim storage of radioactive waste should be available in a nuclear medicine facility. The room should be locked, properly marked and ventilated.

Waste treatment and disposal

Radioactive waste from nuclear medicine procedures can be dealt with either by simply storing the waste safely until radioactive decay has reduced the activity to a safe level or possibly by disposal of low activity waste into the sewage system. Long half-life or high activity waste may need long term storage in a suitable storage area. Technetium-99m waste normally

requires storage for only 48 hours, in a plastic bag inside a shielded container. The container should be labelled with the radionuclide and date. Gallium-67, I-131 and other longer half-life materials should be placed in a separate labelled and dated plastic bag and stored safely. Following the above considerations, the following summary of practical advice for concrete items used in nuclear medicine can be given; Technetium generators in two options, (1) returning to the supplier after use and (2) waiting for decay and dismantling of the elution column afterwards. After a waiting time of 1.5-2 months, when the activity and the dose rate are so low that the elution column can be removed, the generator can be dismantled and the material be considered as non-radioactive. Labels should then be removed. Used syringes and needles; These can be collected in a shielded container in the rooms used for preparation and injection of radiopharmaceuticals. When the container is full, it should be sealed and the expected disposal date be marked on it. After this time, the external dose rate can be monitored. The container can be disposed of when the external ambient dose equivalent rate is the same as the background. Gloves and cover paper; These should be collected in plastic bags in the rooms used for preparation and injection of radiopharmaceuticals. When a bag is filled, it should be sealed. After waiting for decay, they can be disposed of as ordinary waste. Sealed sources for calibration of activity meters, quality control of gamma cameras and counters, and anatomical marking of images: After waiting for decay, the RPO should determine the disposal route according to radioactive waste management regulation. Patient's excreta, such as urine with I-131. For diagnostic patients there is no need for collection of excreta and ordinary toilets can be used. For therapy patients use separate toilets equipped with delay tanks

Conclusions and Suggestions

The use of unsealed radionuclides in medicine is increasing throughout Albania as therapeutic and diagnostic radiopharmaceuticals as well as positron emission tomography (PET) imaging are becoming more common in the clinical environment. The fundamentals of justification and optimization must apply when undertaking nuclear medicine procedures. Exposure to radiation during a medical procedure needs to be justified by weighing up the benefits against the detriments that may be caused. This includes considering the benefits and risks of alternative methods that do not involve any exposure to radiation. In the case of optimization, practitioners

need to ensure that the minimum amount of radiation is used to achieve the intended diagnostic objective. This paper encourages the use of Diagnostic Reference Levels (DRLs) as a tool to support optimization of protection to the patient. The protection of occupationally exposed staff and the public are also an important aspect of the optimal use of ionizing radiation in medicine. Special concern in relation to radiation protection is afforded to children, and pregnant or potentially pregnant females.

References

1. Sang-Geon Cho, et al “Radiation Safety in Nuclear Medicine Procedures”, Springer Nature Link, 19 February 2016, Volume 51, pages 11–16, (2017) <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13139-016-0406-0?fromPaywallRec=true>
2. Simon R. Cherry, James A. Sorenson and Michael E. Phelps, “Physics in Nuclear Medicine”, Science Direct, Book (Fourth Edition) 2012, page 427.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-1-4160-5198-5.00023-X>
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/book/monograph/9781416051985/physics-in-nuclear-medicine>

3. R Ravichandran et al., “An overview of radioactive waste disposal procedures of a nuclear medicine department”, J Med Phys. 2011 Apr-Jun;36(2):95–99. doi: 10.4103/0971-6203.79692, <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC3119958/>